

The Reality Of Functional Alienation Among Teachers In General Education Schools In Madina

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 18, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: January 02, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Alienation, Loss Of Values, Loss Of Confidence, Social Isolation</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4411389</p>	<p><i>The study aimed to identify the reality of functional alienation among the teachers of general education in Madinah, and to verify this; the researcher used the descriptive approach. The study sample consisted of (505) teachers from various stages of public education in Madina. The researcher prepared a questionnaire to identify the aspects of reality of functional alienation among the teachers and the extent of their impact on some variables. The tool consisted of (44) paragraphs divided into five fields: the field of loss of standards, the field of loss of confidence, the field of social isolation, the field of loss of control and sense of helplessness, and the field of self-alienation. The tool was developed and verified to ensure its sincerity and stability, and the results showed the following: The spread of functional alienation among teachers of public education in Madinah with a medium degree, considering the value of the average of axes, (3.0). The highest manifestations of alienation appeared in the teachers of public education in Madina, those related to axis (loss of values), and the axis (loss of confidence), Existence of differences of statistical significance at the level of significance $\alpha \leq 0.05$ between the variable (stage), and the manifestations of functional alienation among the teachers of public education in Medina, There are no statistically significant differences between the variable (scientific qualification) and the manifestations of occupational alienation among the teachers of public education in Medina, There were no statistically significant differences between the variable (years of experience), There were statistically significant differences between the variable (specialization) and the manifestations of occupational alienation related to the axes (loss of confidence, and the general axis) for the benefit of the teachers of literary specialization.</i></p>

1. Introduction

Human societies are characterized by many transformations and successive changes in all fields, and these transformations have many repercussions that we cannot ignore, whether on individuals in particular, or on society as a whole. Alienation is one of the most dangerous of these phenomena, as it has become haunting for many societies.

And the phenomenon of alienation has captured the attention of many philosophers and scientists, and perhaps this is due to the extent of its impact on the individual's relationship with everyone around him. Even about himself (Zahi, Nour al-Din, 2013, p. 13), so it was natural that this reflected negatively on all his life activities, with the difference in range between people (Sabr, 2013, p. 250)

There is a variety and variation in the use of the concept of alienation as an implicit consequence of the different philosophical trends that concerned itself with dealing with this concept. It was the first philosophical use of it among the theorists of the "social contract", headed by Jean-Jacques Rusu, who used the concept of alienation of the individual when he talked about rights. Naturalization for the benefit of society (Bo Allama, 2011, p. 11).

Hegel was the first to treat the concept of alienation in German philosophy, and And then came Marx (Marx), "who had the merit in transforming the concept of alienation into a secular, material one. Marx dealt with the alienation that accompanies productive processes from four angles: the alienation of the worker from the product of his work, the alienation of the worker from his work, the alienation of the worker from himself, and the alienation of the worker The worker on behalf of others" (Awaidat, 1995, pp. 79-83), hence we note that alienation refers to a number of diverse relationships; Such as man's relationship with himself, and his relationship with others, with nature, and with human action.

One of the most influential forms of alienation is what is known as functional alienation, as the matter in this is not related to the individual alone. Rather, it extends to the institution, or the entire organization, as the employee's feeling of not belonging to his job negatively affects his performance and outputs, and then on the organisation's outputs and goals.

"Functional alienation is defined as a weak level of integration between the individual and the job, or it is the employee's feeling of estrangement in his workplace, as he loses the functional and organizational affiliation, and he lacks the natural interaction within the work environment" (Sabr, 2013, p. 251).

Thus, we find that alienation in organizations or work establishments is a very dangerous matter. Because it affects the relationship of the employee with the institution in which he works, which must be loyalty to it; Dire consequences for both parties - the employee and the establishment - often end with an unsatisfactory end (Al-Qaidani, 2006, p.8).

There is no doubt that "the phenomenon of alienation has a number of effects, the most important of which are: retreat, marginalization, the decay of identity, isolation, and the weakness of belonging." (Zahi, Nour al-Din, 2013, p.135), as well as slumbering, job neglect, indifference at work, excessive absence of employees, low level of real time in their jobs, waste of time, and their low interaction with their duties and responsibilities, lack of seriousness and sincerity in work and dedication. Working in front of bosses (Al-Qidani, 2006, p. 36).

Despite the tendency of many institutions to provide services that allow employees to have a high level of stability and job security, as well as the presence of modern technologies that guarantee them more well-being and relieve them of many of their work burdens, the results of scientific studies conducted in the various work sectors indicate Until there is functional alienation observed; "In a statistic reported by the British Civil Service Department, it was found that 22% of public sector employees are isolated." (Al-Qatari, 2012, p.9), and at the local level, the study of Al-Thubaiti (2008) found that government employees in public organizations in Jeddah are characterized by job alienation at a medium level, with a rate of 68.8%. Which means the occurrence of a large segment of employees in functional alienation, as well as the study of Al-Mutrafi (2005), one of the most prominent results of which was that functional alienation is clearly spread among workers in the passports of Makkah, and one of the most prominent manifestations of their alienation was: The spread of the phenomenon of slackness in work among employees And manifestations of fatigue, suffering and depression, and the frequent errors and the large number of personal problems among colleagues, and the frequent absence from work without an acceptable excuse.

There is no doubt that the matter becomes more dangerous when it comes to an institution such as a school and an employee such as a teacher, who have been entrusted with a sensitive task for all societies, which is education, education and the upbringing of generations, where some teachers face many conditions related to the nature of their education, whether from the technical or administrative side, School work, which would have a negative impact on the teacher, and then on his educational performance and his dealings with students, as the job alienation of teachers is not limited to them only; Rather, it lengthens students, and affects the outcomes of educational work.

The topic of functional alienation is one of the most important topics that have occupied the interest of many researchers and thinkers. Therefore, we find there are many Arab and foreign researches that have tried to shed light on this topic from different angles, and these research will be addressed as follows:

A study (Tajouri, 2011) entitled: The functional alienation of teachers of basic education schools in Benghazi in light of some variables.

The study aimed to identify the level of functional alienation among a sample of teachers of basic education schools in Benghazi during the academic year (2009-2010), and whether there are differences between the sample members in the degree of their exposure to functional alienation, attributable to variables: gender, educational qualification, Experience, specialization, and academic stage, and the study concluded the following results: Basic education school teachers are exposed to functional alienation during the exercise of their work with high grades on the scale dimensions in general except after disability, the presence of an inverse relationship that is not statistically significant between functional alienation and experience, the absence of relevant differences Statistical significance attributed to variables: gender, educational qualification, specialization, and academic stage.

-Al-Hamdani and Al-Sarraf study (2012) entitled: The relationship between some personal variables and a sense of functional alienation: an exploratory study of the opinions of primary school teachers in Nineveh Governorate.

The study aimed to determine the relationship between some personal variables: (age, gender, academic achievement, length of service, marital status) for school teachers, with the dimensions of functional alienation, and among the most prominent results of the study: the presence of high correlation relationships between the personal variables, with the dimensions of Functional alienation, as well as the existence of compatibility between personal variables and the dimensions of functional alienation, and this indicates the strength of the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

-An interview study, Hawamdeh, and Tarawneh (2012) entitled: Level of functional alienation among teachers of government secondary schools in the Amman Governorate from their point of view.

The study aimed to identify the level of functional alienation among public school teachers in Amman, Jordan, and their point of view, and the results showed; The functional alienation of public secondary school teachers in

the Amman governorate was average, and the results indicated that there were no statistically significant differences in the level of alienation due to the variables of sex, experience, and educational qualification.

Abu Al-Haija's study (2013) entitled: Manifestations of functional alienation among educational counselors from their point of view.

The study aimed to identify the aspects of functional alienation among educational counselors from their point of view, and the results of the study highlighted: that the manifestations of functional alienation among educational counselors from their point of view came in a low degree, and the highest was an area of loss of standards, and the lowest was an area of loss of control. Statistically significant differences in the manifestations of functional alienation due to the gender variable, and statistically significant differences appeared in the aspects of job alienation among counselors attributed to the variable of years of service, in favor of educational counselors who have less experience in the field of loss of control.

-A study (Al-Hawas, 2017) entitled: The Impact of Social Responsibility on the Feeling of Functional Alienation among Primary School Principals: An Applied Study in M'sila State.

The study aimed to identify the degree of the impact of social responsibility (inside the school - outside the school), and the study reached a number of results, including: That there is a statistically significant effect of social responsibility on the feeling of functional alienation, that is, the higher the values of the social responsibility variable, the greater the sense of functional alienation.

Study problem and questions:

Functional alienation is an indicator that the institution is going through a real crisis. "It means that the employees of the institution come to a decision that the institution in which they work is no longer the right place for them to work for various reasons, and there is no doubt that the employee's alienation and dissatisfaction with his work has a negative impact on work, such as the effect on the absence rate, on the relationship between colleagues, and the relationship With the administration, and the relationship with the public of beneficiaries "(Al-Matrafi, 2005, pp. 57 -60).

The teaching profession is one of the most important professions that provide society with qualified scientific, social, artistic and ethical human elements, which are well prepared on good scientific foundations and rules.

And on the importance of the issue of functional alienation in the educational milieu, as teachers form the largest segment of state employees in Saudi society, and thus the repercussions of this phenomenon will affect all segments of society, as the case has not yet been scientifically presented, and local studies have not been found that dealt with aspects of The functional alienation of the teachers' category is the same as the study of Al-Subaie (2010), which came under the title Degree of Effectiveness of Performance and its Relationship with Functional Alienation of Secondary School Teachers in Makkah - according to the search in Scholar Google, as well as Arabic databases.

The current study chose the Medina region as a model for a number of considerations, the first of which is that it is the residence of the researcher, and secondly, because it is considered the fourth most populated city in the Kingdom, not to mention its cultural and religious standing.

Based on the above, the current study tries to answer the following main question:

What is the reality of the job alienation of female teachers in public education schools in Medina?

From this branch the following questions:

What is the prevalence of manifestations of functional alienation among female teachers in public education schools in Medina?

Are there differences at the level of significance $\alpha \leq 0.05$ between the degree of prevalence of the manifestations of functional alienation among female teachers in public education schools in the enlightened city, attributable to variables (academic stage, academic qualification, years of experience, and specialization)?

Objectives of the study :

The current study aims to:

- 1 -Exposing the reality of the functional alienation of female teachers in public education schools in Medina.
- 2 -Detecting the degree of prevalence of functional alienation among teachers in public education schools in Medina.
- 3 -Knowing the statistically significant differences between the degree of prevalence of the manifestations of functional alienation among female teachers in public education schools in the enlightened city, and some independent variables (school stage, academic qualification, years of experience, and specialization).
- 4 -It is hoped that the results of this study will arouse the interest of officials in the Education Department. To find out about the phenomenon of teachers' functional alienation, and to take the necessary measures towards it.
- 6 -This study can pave the way for subsequent research that enriches knowledge in the field of functional alienation in the educational field, and those aimed at finding solutions that would reduce the effects of functional alienation in educational institutions.

Method and procedures

The study community:

The current study community consisted of all the (10,500) teachers in public education schools in the city of Munawwarah, with (5007) teachers from the (elementary level) teachers, who were (47.68%), and (5493) teachers from the (intermediate and secondary) levels) It makes up (52.32%).

The study sample:

The sample consisted of (550) teachers. The sample data were collected using the cluster method in selecting schools, as two schools were randomly drawn from each education office in the city of Illinois.

Study Approach:

The study used the descriptive survey method. Because it is the most appropriate approach for the current study, in terms of data collection, analysis, and processing, in order to reach the required results.

Study tool:

This study relies on the Questionnaire as a tool to collect data that answers the study questions.

Building the tool in its final form:

The questionnaire consisted of (44) statements distributed into (5) fields as follows:

- The field of losing criteria, and it consists of (9) phrases.

- The field of loss of confidence, and consists of (10) phrases.

The field of social isolation, and it consists of (7) phrases.

- The domain of loss of control and a feeling of powerlessness, and it consists of (10) phrases.

- The field of self-estrangement, consisting of (8) phrases, and the response to the paragraphs was measured through a five-point scale (always, often, sometimes, rarely, never)

To ensure the validity of the instrument, and that it is intended to measure the phenomenon. It was presented to a group of arbitrators, among whom (20) arbitrators responded about:

- The relevance of the paragraphs to the field of study.

- The clarity of the phrases.

- The integrity of the phrasing.

Any amendments or proposals that they deem appropriate.

To ensure the internal consistency of the tool; The value of Cronbach's Alpha was found to measure the validity of the correlation between the degree of each statement and the total score of the axis to which it belongs, as well as the validity of the correlation coefficients between the total score of the axis and the overall degree of the questionnaire. The value of the Cronbach's alpha coefficient was (0.88).

The value of the stability coefficient was calculated as Pearson(.94)

Study results and discussion

Results related to the answer to the first question of the study, which is:

- What is the reality of the manifestations of functional alienation of female teachers in public education schools in Medina?

To answer this question; The researcher analyzed the responses of the sample members, and identified the arithmetic means and standard deviations. In order to interpret the values of the averages for the expressions included in the questionnaire after validation and reliability of them, the following is the interpretation of the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the sample responses for each axis separately:

That the criterion loss of criteria obtained the highest average compared to the rest of the axes, with a score of (3.2). With the multiple pressures that the teacher suffers from her work as a teacher; She is facing pressure from the academic level of female students, and the rules that she must adhere to in her dealings with female students, not to mention the standards and demands related to the scientific subject. The teacher's sense of all these pressures and responsibilities, and not finding them in the values of the noble profession that relieves her of this dilemma and makes her feel safe in the job, may lead her to resort to negative values that contradict the values of the profession, and there may be an outbreak of these values among the teachers in the school, And it has become the natural solution to get rid of pressures, which was confirmed (Khalifa, 2013) that it is a result of the pressures and transformations that people suffer in various areas of life He began to perceive failure to adhere to positive values and standards in his behavior as desirable, in light of the social context in which he lives. This is because he realized, in light of his experiences with the facts of reality, that his adherence to and commitment to positive values and ideals does not enable him to reconcile and coexist with these pressures. Because his lack of commitment and the adoption of distorted values is the safety and mechanism that enables him to maintain his survival and satisfy his needs that the society has been unable to satisfy, and with this result, the current study is in agreement with the study (Al-Sarraf, 2012) where one of its results was the (loss of standards) axis. A higher average than the rest of the other axes, as it was found that the sample has a high feeling of not accepting the prevailing standards in the workplace, and thus it is difficult for it to adapt to those standards.

- Loss of confidence.

That the loss of confidence axis got the highest average, compared to the rest of the axes, as it got an arithmetic mean of (3.2).

This result is consistent with the study (Al-Sarraf, 2012), where one of its results was an appearance (loss of confidence or loss of meaning) on a high average, as it was found that the sample lacked confidence in its career life, with a weak relationship between what it does, and the researcher attributes The loss of confidence axis obtained the highest average compared to the rest of the axes, until the teacher in public education schools in Medina has lost confidence in the school community. As a result of her commitment to certain standards to deal with female students, the lack of clarity of standards related to the evaluation of her performance, as well as the many burdens placed on the teacher, in contrast to the renewed demands of her profession, with poor communication between her and officials in the educational sector, and not allowing her to express an opinion on what is related to current educational issues, And her commitment to certain teaching methods that may not be commensurate with her capabilities and inclinations, and her lack of involvement in decisions related to the field of education, or the lack of clarity of those decisions and their importance to the scientific field, this may be a guarantee of the teacher losing confidence in the educational community and the school. This was confirmed by (Khalifa, 2013), where he explained that the restrictions and limitations that individuals face are what make them feel alienated, and hence prevent their creativity and the launch of their creative ideas. Alienation stands as a stumbling block in front of the individual's creativity, knowledge of himself and his abilities, and in contrast, freedom, liberation, and laws can reduce feelings of alienation, and create a sense of belonging and the feeling that life has meaning and value.

- Axis of social isolation:

The Social Isolation Ax ranked last compared to the rest of the axes, as it obtained an arithmetic mean of (2.4). As for the paragraphs of this axis, their scores varied according to their arithmetic averages. With regard to obtaining the phrase: (I prefer that my relationships within the school be formal) at the highest arithmetic mean, reaching (3.2), which means that female teachers in public education schools prefer formal relationships within the school rather than private friendships.

The researcher explains this result that the nature of the school community and the nature of work in it, and the relationship of teachers with the administration in the school, are what led to the loss of the spirit of cooperation, love and harmony, and imposed on them the control of feelings of self-love, loss of confidence, and competition outside the required natural limits, which may lead to some teachers To the use of illegal methods of giving birth from the administration and officials or obtaining

. The second question of the study: Does the degree of the prevalence of functional alienation manifestations of female teachers differ in public education schools in the enlightened city, according to the different study variables (Teaching stage, , specialization) at the significance level of $\alpha \leq 0.05$?

To answer this question, and to know the effect of each of the effects - the academic stage, academic qualification, years of experience, and specialization - on the prevalence of manifestations of functional alienation among teachers in public education schools in the city - the researcher calculated the arithmetic averages and standard deviations, and the (T) test ; To study differences between sample responses.

First: The effect of (the school stage) on the manifestations of functional alienation among public education teachers in Medina.

To find out the extent of the impact of the school stage on the manifestations of functional alienation among public education teachers in Medina; The researcher calculated the arithmetic means, standard deviations, and (T) test for the variable of the school stage, means, standard deviations, and (T) value of the school stage variable

we find that there are differences in the aspects of functional alienation among public education teachers in the enlightened city due to the stage variable, in the axis of loss of control and feeling helpless, the axis of self-estrangement, and the general axis, in favor of post-primary school teachers.

The researcher attributes the existence of statistical significance in favor of (post-primary) teachers in the axis of loss of standards, the axis of social isolation, the axis of loss of control, as well as the axis of self-estrangement, compared to the (primary) stage that the teachers in the (post-elementary stage) deal with The most difficult stages of life require dealing with them according to the characteristics of their development in order to ensure that their problems are solved, their friendship is gained, and their abilities are developed.

The teacher in the (post-elementary) stage has a special responsibility to deal with a student going through adolescence. So that the student can pass safely during this period, away from behavioral deviations, and not fall prey to some mental illnesses, not to mention the need for her to endure the behavior and behavior of students at that age stage; Where the adolescent is sensitive to criticism of others, and does not control her emotions, as she tends to be independent in her affairs, and does not prefer the interference of others in her affairs, and her personality is dominated by mood swings, introversion, isolation, aggression, and a strong attachment to this This would pose great pressure on them, especially in light of its responsibility to the administration for the low level of students through the evaluation of job performance, as they are required to form a balanced and

moderate relationship with them, and this is confirmed by (Al-Otaibi, 2007), where he mentioned that the bad relations between teachers and students, which involve The lack of respect and mutual appreciation negatively affects the performance of the teacher, and then on the students' acceptance of him and their level of academic achievement.

The effect of (specialization) on the manifestations of the prevalence of functional alienation:

To know the extent of the effect of the specialization variable on the manifestations of functional alienation among public education teachers in the enlightened city; The researcher calculated the arithmetic means, standard deviations, and (T) test of the variable of specialization,

means, standard deviations, and (T) value of the specialization variable

we find that there are statistically significant differences in the axis of loss of confidence and the general axis between female teachers according to the specialization variable in favor of those with literary specializations. Meaning: The average paragraphs of the Axis of Loss of Confidence for female teachers with a literary specialization exceeds the female teachers who specialize in scientifically.

The researcher believes that the reason behind this result, which is the existence of statistically significant differences in the axis of loss of confidence, and the general axis, between female teachers according to the variable of specialization, in favor of those with literary specializations - is the nature of the courses in the literary department, which depend heavily on the method of teaching them on indoctrination. And then preservation, and then the teacher does not have the opportunity to innovate and innovate in a way that ensures her renewal and lack of stereotyping in teaching, as in teaching scientific courses that allow high levels of thinking, analysis, creativity in presenting information, and innovation in presenting it, and she may suffer from the view of society Literary majors, which are viewed as being of less value than scientific disciplines.

Study results, recommendations and suggestions

Results:

The study reached a number of results, namely:

- The spread of job alienation among public education teachers in the enlightened city, to a moderate degree.
- The highest manifestations of alienation appearing among public education teachers in the enlightened city, those related to the axis (loss of values) and the axis (loss of confidence).
- The presence of statistically significant differences between the variable (stage), and the manifestations of functional alienation among public education teachers in the enlightened city, in favor of the post-primary stage.
- There are no statistically significant differences between the variable (academic qualification) and the manifestations of functional alienation among public education teachers in Madinah.
- There are no statistically significant differences between the variable (years of experience) and the manifestations of functional alienation among public education teachers in Medina.
- There are statistically significant differences between the variable (specialization), and the manifestations of functional alienation, among public education teachers in Medina, in favor of literary specialization.
- One of the most important reasons that limited the emergence of job alienation among public education teachers in the enlightened city was the teachers' awareness of the status and honor of their profession, and pride in it.
- One of the most important reasons for the spread of functional alienation among public education teachers in Al-Madinah Al-Munawwarah is the lack of good communication between female teachers and between school principals and officials in the educational field, their lack of participation in decision-making, and their updating of the latest developments.

Study recommendations:

The study reached a number of recommendations, as follows:

Activating effective communication between school principals and officials in the educational field and between female teachers, with each other.

Preparing training programs aimed at educating teachers about the phenomenon of functional alienation, its concept, and its causes.

Taking into account alleviation of work pressure on female teachers, and the distribution of tasks among them according to their specializations.

Giving teachers specific responsibilities, and providing them with information and notes about the mission.

Involving female teachers in decision-making and informing them of all variables in the educational field.

Raising the level of good preparation for female students in colleges of education, in order to qualify them for the teaching profession; Because good preparation will help the teacher to withstand work pressures, and to behave well in different educational situations.

Study Recommendations:

- Conducting a similar study with other variables not discussed in the current study. Such as variable (job rank), variable (marital status), and variable (age).

Conducting a comparative study between the prevalence of alienation among female teachers in public schools and private school teachers.

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